

STRATEGIES ON HANDLING TRANSLATOR'S FALSE FRIENDS IN CLASSROOM

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This article discusses the phenomenon of translator's false friends and how it can affect students learning a foreign language. False friends are words that look or sound similar in two languages but have different meanings. They can cause confusion and often lead to mistakes in translation. The impact of false friends on language learners is also discussed, with a focus on how they can hinder understanding, lead to errors, and ultimately impede language acquisition. Strategies for identifying and avoiding false friends are presented, including the importance of context, using a bilingual dictionary, and seeking clarification from native speakers. Overall, the article emphasizes the importance of recognizing and addressing false friends in language learning to improve accuracy and fluency.

Keywords: *translator's false friends, cognates, extensive reading, translation competence, guided learning*

Because our studied phenomenon is known as «translator's false friends,» it is natural to believe that the translators are the ones most affected by the complexity of these words/expressions. Nevertheless, once you reach a certain level of English, it becomes evident that this vocabulary category does not adversely affect professionals the most. The category that has to deal with the problematic side of these words is students, which refers to people who are studying a foreign language, in this case English. The native language becomes an impediment to learning new vocabulary, grammatical, semantic, and syntactical patterns in this situation. Even though translators and interpreters are not the most inconvenienced, there are situations in which they may experience chal-

lenges when translating due the fact the vocabulary patterns of so called “false friends” are unlimited and require experience and professionalism in their acknowledgement.

Since we established the affected part, we should mention some of the ways a teacher could teach and assure his students a decent vocabulary in identifying the phenomenon in discussion.

Since «false friends» are largely a vocabulary issue, a teacher should utilize methods and tactics to help his students recognize words, be aware of their contexts, and consult dictionaries when translating, conversing, or utilizing the English language. Because of their common usage and Greek and Latin roots, as well as other influences, TFF terms are found throughout the English language’s various lexical strata.

In their book «Teaching vocabulary» [12], Nation and Newton examine the quantity of words one needs to learn in order to communicate effectively when learning a foreign language. They have provided a table that illustrates an effective communication procedure in mathematical patterns [12, p. 238]:

<i>Level</i>	<i>Number of Words</i>	<i>Text Coverage %</i>
High-frequency words	2000	87
Academic vocabulary	800	8
Technical vocabulary	2000	3
Total to be learned	4800	98
Low-frequency words	123.200	2
<i>Total</i>	<i>128.000</i>	<i>100</i>

In selecting vocabulary for teaching, a teacher, author of manual should keep in mind some criteria that are required. These are:

Range	the extent to which a word occurs in the different types of texts
Coverage	the capacity of a word to replace other words
Frequency	the number of occurrences of a word in the target language
Learnability	the extent to which a word can be learned without difficulty
Language needs	the extent to which a word is regarded as “required” by the learner in order to communicate

Vocabulary instruction above the basic level has typically been accidental, confined to introducing new words as they arose in reading or occasionally hearing readings. This method of teaching vocabulary infers that it will grow as a result of using other language abilities, although it has been shown that this is insufficient to guarantee vocabulary growth.

Today, it is generally agreed that vocabulary instruction should be included in the curriculum and given on a regular basis. Lewis [9, p. 56] is one author who makes the case that vocabulary instruction should take precedence over grammar instruction since “language consists of grammaticalized lexis, not lexicalized grammar.”

There are several aspects of lexis that need to be taken into account when teaching vocabulary. The list below is based on the work of Gairns and Redman [6, p. 85]:

- *Boundaries between conceptual meaning: knowing not only what lexis refers to, but also where the boundaries are that separate it from words of related meaning (e.g. cup, mug, bowl).*
- *Polysemy: distinguishing between the various meaning of a single word form with several but closely related meanings (head: of a person, of a pin, of an organisation).*
- *Homonymy: distinguishing between the various meaning of a single word form which has several meanings which are NOT closely related (e.g. a file: used to put papers in or a tool).*
- *Homophony: understanding words that have the same pronunciation but different spellings and meanings (e.g. flour, flower).*
- *Synonymy: distinguishing between the different shades of meaning that synonymous words have (e.g. extend, increase, expand).*
- *Affective meaning: distinguishing between the attitudinal and emotional factors (denotation and connotation), which depend on the speakers attitude or the situation. Socio-cultural associations of lexical items is another important factor.*
- *Style, register, dialect: Being able to distinguish between different levels of formality, the effect of different contexts and topics, as well as differences in geographical variation.*

- *Translation*: **awareness of certain differences and similarities between the native and the foreign language (e.g. false cognates).**
- *Chunks of language*: **multi-word verbs, idioms, strong and weak collocations, lexical phrases.**
- *Grammar of vocabulary*: **learning the rules that enable students to build up different forms of the word or even different words from that word (e.g. sleep, slept, sleeping; able, unable; disability).**
- *Pronunciation*: **ability to recognise and reproduce items in speech.**

The relevance of the teaching factors previously discussed is that vocabulary teaching objectives must go beyond just covering a predetermined number of words on a word list. We must employ instructional strategies that can assist students understand this broad definition of what it means to understand a lexical term. Additionally, we must go above and above by providing opportunities for students to put what they have learned to use and by assisting them in using efficient written storage methods.

When presenting a new word to students, teachers follow a scheme, plan, that establishes the steps of making acquainted with the new vocabulary item [6] :

- concise definition (as in a dictionary; often a superordinate with qualifications: for example, a cat is an animal which...)
- detailed description (of appearance, qualities...)
- examples (hyponyms)
- illustration (picture, object)
- demonstration (acting, mime)
- context (story or sentence in which the item occurs)
- synonyms
- opposites(s) (antonyms)
- translation
- associated ideas, collocations.

We observe that the step “translation” is almost at the end. Therefore, the student needs a definition, examples (words belonging to the same

class/range/type), a context, and finally a translation. When the aforementioned steps are taken, the TFF phenomenon becomes less intense, but at a certain level, words are studied directly from texts, contexts, and parts of speech. Errors are still possible in this situation, but they're simpler to spot and prevent. But if, during a speech or discussion, someone uses words from their mother tongue that they are confident they can "see" in the foreign language they are learning while also adding (in our case, a different pronunciation from what is required by the rules), it could create an amusing, confusing, or awkward situation. The most effective methods for learning vocabulary and speech patterns in a foreign language are communicative situations and reading exercises done with a dictionary. Natural communication is the most often used method because of the factors like:

- Much of the lexical and semantic information cannot be or is not described and taught as explicit knowledge
- There is too much information involved in vocabulary that it is just impossible to teach it all.
- What is taught does not necessarily lead to lexical competence on the learner's part.

A reader may acquire the ability of correctness in using the vocabulary through:

Once you have gained an advanced knowledge of various roots, you can enhance your vocabulary study. If you don't master the roots early on, you will have a difficult time with improving your vocabulary. As you are learning the roots, you will want to touch on the vocabulary a bit. It is basically an issue of phonics combined with spelling. When these two factors are developed in conjunction with each other, you have the structure that will allow your vocabulary to become much more impressive. You have also probably heard people talk about the importance of reading. Reading is the best way to improve your vocabulary, and it is also fun. You will want to be selective in the books you choose to read. While many people enjoy reading fiction books, non-fiction books are much more effective when it comes to enhancing your vocabulary. There are a number of reasons for this. Fiction books will generally be written for the purpose of entertainment.

While they can allow a person to increase their vocabulary much more than someone who doesn't read, they will not help you as much as non-fiction books. Non-fiction books tend to be written on concepts that are challenging, and their tone is more formal.

Although challenging is sometimes actually a good technique, especially when dealing with abstract words like "happiness" or "luck" or "travel". Words should be used in a real setting or context. Don't forget to help them find useful strategies for memorizing words. Give them relevant exercises based on how they can consolidate what they are learning. At the same time, try to motivate them and arouse their interest. In our opinion, the most important thing when teaching advanced vocabulary is to promote learner independence so that students can process new vocabulary and expand their vocabulary after the course is over. Therefore, guided search, contextual guessing and the use of dictionaries should be the main ways to deal with meaning discovery, thus avoiding the TFF phenomenon and many other issues related to the correct use of vocabulary.

Guided discovery includes questions or examples to help students correctly guess the meanings. In this way, learners can engage in semantic processing that aids learning and retention. Contextual guessing means using the context in which a word appears to give an idea of its meaning,

or in some cases guessing from the word itself, as with words of Latin origin. Knowing about vocabulary, such as prefixes and suffixes, can also help students find meaning. Teachers can help students use special techniques and practice context-based guessing, such as understanding discourses and identifying the function of a word in a sentence (eg verb, adjective, noun). The latter is also very useful when using dictionaries.

As soon as feasible, beginning in Intermediate level and up, students should use EFL dictionaries. With the right instruction, dictionaries can be a helpful tool for students, enabling them to work independently. Students can verify pronunciation, the word's syntax (such as verb patterns, verb forms, plurality, comparatives, etc.), different spellings (American versus British), style and register, as well as examples that show usage, in addition to understanding meaning.

Teachers should improve pupils' awareness of the danger of words sounding familiar given that such terms are challenging. This is simplest to perform when translating something since then it can be made obvious that there are a specific amount of "false friends" that need to be detected and the errors may be avoided by using synonyms. However, this method of looking for a synonym for terms that sound too similar to someone's native tongue might be a useful technique to steer clear of false friends at any time.

Direct, live translation, however, or face-to-face interactions, require far more conscious and lasting control to the point where it is possible to instantly identify, become aware of, and locate a replacement for a word that could be troublesome. Unless the individual speaking is a very skilled speaker of English as a foreign language, such an endeavor not only hinders fluency and clarity of communication but also proves to be unachievable for the average speaker and student. Being constantly on the lookout for errors is not a proper way to conduct a conversation. The risk of over caring resides in this as well as the possibility that some errors related to the employment of "false friends" may ultimately be more endearing or simpler to comprehend. After all, the collocutor may already be aware of the similarity that prompted your inappropriate choice of words, and he or she will find it less bothersome than a slow, time-consuming interrupted and stumbling flow of too carefully (and possibly still

unsuccessfully) selected words, resulting in a tedious and poor excuse of dialogue.

The smallest thing that can be done, and the closest thing to the ideal answer, is to teach the most prevalent false friends in English lessons, the same way every other problematic English idiom or difference between British and American English are.

As a result, awareness is guaranteed, which should be the first step in avoiding awkward conversational circumstances and in conquering the aversion to speaking—at least the one brought on by a lack of this specific knowledge. Is the use of the phrase “false friends” actually a problem? Yes, it becomes annoying for native English speakers when the word sounds forced or the conversation is foreign. Such errors aren’t supposed to be tolerated in the academic community or among language experts. However, aside from the fact that it boosts the confidence and fluency of speakers of less-than-perfect English, giving them the impression that they are able to communicate, the entire process of substituting a word with a meaning close to one found in the mother language for the right one, may be seen as part of the tendency of globalization and uniformity of language.

“Textbooks’ treatment of cognates is examined, and some problems arising from overemphasis on use of true cognates are noted, including potential for stilted language use and the danger of adopting false cognates. It is recommended that the teaching of false cognates be included in ESL instruction, to promote vocabulary development” [7]. Techniques involve teachers using standard language exercises and wrong word identification games to create collections of wrong words and incorporate them into the classroom.

Another strategy for advanced learners is to turn receptive vocabulary into productive vocabulary. This requires further refinement of subject understanding and exploration of boundaries such as conceptual meaning, ambiguity, synonyms, style, registers and possible collocations so that students can use the subject correctly. Vocabulary items are most likely to be learned when the learner feels a personal need to know about them, or when the learner needs to express something to achieve his or her own goals. It must be considered when This means that the decision

to include a word in a productive vocabulary is entirely personal and depends on each student's motivations and needs. Logically, production will depend on motivation, and this is what teachers should aim at promoting, based on their awareness of students needs and preferences. Task-based learning should help teachers to provide authentic, meaningful tasks in which students engage to achieve a concrete output, using appropriate language for the context.

We could not talk about vocabulary teaching nowadays without mentioning Lewis [8, p.195], whose controversial, thought-provoking ideas have been shaking the ELT world since its publication. His most important contribution was to highlight the importance of vocabulary as being basic to communication. We do agree that if learners do not recognise the meaning of keywords they will be unable to participate in the conversation, even if they know the morphology and syntax. On the other hand, we believe that grammar is equally important in teaching, and therefore in our opinion, it is not the case to substitute grammar teaching with vocabulary teaching, but that both should be present in teaching a foreign language.

Lewis himself insists that his lexical approach is not simply a shift of emphasis from grammar to vocabulary teaching, as 'language consists not of traditional grammar and vocabulary, but often of multi-word pre-fabricated chunks' [8, p. 203]. Chunks include collocations, fixed and semi-fixed expressions and idioms, and according to him, occupy a crucial role in facilitating language production, being the key to fluency.

An explanation for native speakers' fluency is that vocabulary is not stored only as individual words, but also as parts of phrases and larger chunks, which can be retrieved from memory as a whole, reducing processing difficulties. On the other hand, learners who only learn individual words will need a lot more time and effort to express themselves.

Consequently, it is essential to make students aware of chunks, giving them opportunities to identify, organise and record these. Identifying chunks is not always easy, and at least in the beginning, students need a lot of guidance.

The same author [8, p. 219] explains that most learners with 'good vocabularies' have problems with fluency because their 'collocational

competence' is very limited, and that, especially from Intermediate level, we should aim at increasing their collocational competence with the vocabulary they have already got. For Advance learners he also suggests building on what they already know, using better strategies and increasing the number of items they meet outside the classroom. The idea of what it is to 'know' a word is also enriched with the collocational component. According to Lewis [8, 225] 'being able to use a word involves mastering its collocational range and restrictions on that range'. I can say that using all the opportunities to teach chunks rather than isolated words is a feasible idea that has been working well in my classes, and which is fortunately coming up in new coursebooks we are using. However, both teachers and learners need awareness raising activities to be able to identify multi-word chunks.

Apart from identifying chunks, it is important to establish clear ways of organising and recording vocabulary. As mentioned by the same author [14, p. 229], 'language should be recorded together which characteristically occurs together', which means not in a linear, alphabetical order, but in collocation tables, mind-maps, word trees, for example. He also suggests the recording of whole sentences, to help contextualization, and that storage of items is highly personal, depending on each student's needs.

We have already mentioned the use of dictionaries as a way to discover meaning and foster learner independence. Lewis extends the use of dictionaries to focus on word grammar and collocation range, although most dictionaries are rather limited in these.

Lewis also defends the use of 'real' or 'authentic' material from the early stages of learning, because 'acquisition is facilitated by material which is only partly understood' [8, p. 186] Although he does not supply evidence for this, I agree that students need to be given tasks they can accomplish without understanding everything from a given text, because this is what they will need as users of the language. He also suggests that it is better to work intensively with short extracts of authentic material, so they are not too daunting for students and can be explored for collocations.

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